

A Study on Employee Motivation at Solara Active Pharma Science Limited Sipcot Cuddalore

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ABSTRACT

Motivation is based on growth needs. It effect on the minds of individuals and the benefits it generates over a period of time. Motivation represents those forces which act within people giving them specific goal oriented behaviour motivation can be said to be the consequence of an interaction between the individual and the situation. The objective of the study is to find the level of employee motivation and to find the relationship between employee motivation and employee performance at Solara active pharma science limited. The descriptive type of research is used in this study. The rules and policies should be design by the organization and the employee to work well and appreciate them on their tasks fulfilment and achievements. This will surely lead to organizational growth. It improves both their effectiveness and efficiency for the achievement of the organizational goals. The primary and secondary data are used for this study. The tool used is correlation. The population size is 120 and the sample size is 60.

KEYWORDS: Employee motivation, Employee performance, organisational growth and job satisfaction

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I. INTRODUCTION

According to Robert Dubin (1970) has defined motivation as “ the complex of forces starting and keeping a person at work in an organisation. Motivation is something that moves the person to action and continues him in the course of action already initiated”.

According to Dalton, Mc Farland (1974) defines, “motivation refers to the way which urges, drives, desires, aspirations and strivings or needs direct, control or explain the behaviour of human beings”.

According to Mamoria (1995) defines, motivation is a willingness to expend energy to achieve a goal or reward. It is a force that activates dormant engeries and set in motion the action of the people. It is the function that kindles a burning passion for action among the human beings of an organisation.

II. Objectives for the study

1. To find the level of employee motivation at solara active pharma science limited.
2. To find the relationship between employee motivation and employee performance at solara active pharma science limited.

III. Hypothesis for the study

1. H_0 : There is no relationship between employee motivation and employee’s performance.

IV. Review of literature

Nabi & Islam (2017) Motivation indeed has a momentous effect on employee performance. the factors taken into account during the survey Extrinsic factors, Job enrichment and performance appraisal, Relationships and job security, Authority in decision making, Growth opportunity etc.), pragmatically dominates employees’ have to achieve goals of the respective organization. The factors of motivation are salary, monetary incentives and compensation package. The result evidently represented the tangible sorting of how motivation is responsible for up liftment of employee performance. It was found that the connection between motivation and performance is quite natural if not obvious.

Madi (2017) This study has investigated relationship between employee motivation and the three variables of organizational commitment namely, affective, continuance and normative organizational commitment .this study revealed that there is significant impact from employee motivation of front line employees of retailers stores in an organizational commitment.

Nguyen (2017) Motivation of employees play vital role in an organisations effectiveness and assertively contributes to its growth and prosperties. The study conformed that the motivation of employee is affected by two main factors are intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Motivation of employees not only the factors and also an important determinant for job retention.

Nizam & Shah(2015) Employees always seek to be recognised and rewarded this is the important factor which reflect positively on the performance of employees that improves motivation and results in delivering more than the required amount of output and result in higher degree of efficiency.

Ackah (2014) Motivation is the internal process leading to behaviour to satisfy the employees needs. Motivated employees help organisation survive as motivated employees are more productive. They also need to recognize basic need theories that help with these issues.

Shoraj&Llaci(2015) “good communication between superiors and subordinates fosters increase in motivation.” the hypothesis established to test the relation of variables, such as satisfaction at work and increase in motivation the main factors affecting the increase in the motivation of employees are remunerations and especially financial ones, as well as good communication between superiors and subordinates. The satisfaction at work does not play a significant role in the increase in their motivation.

Singh (2017) Motivated employee is a valuable asset, who can deliver immense value to the organization in maintaining and strengthening it business and revenue growth. Contemporary managers have to face and deal with it to obtain organizational success. In employee motivation, managers have to recognize the imperativeness of employee and differences in individual needs. The organisation need to be aware of a variety of employee motivational factors and changes in priorities of these factors overtime. Managers have to enhance their ability to identify rewards system that can be matched with employee needs.

V. Research methodology

A research design is a plan that specifies the objectives of the study, this method have to be adopted in the data collection, tools in data analysis and hypothesis to be framed. The sample for the study is 60 is taken for the study. The sampling technique followed in the study is simple random sampling. The primary and secondary data are used in this study. The primary data were collected form the employees working in solara active pharma limited. The statistical tool correlation is used in this study.

VI. Analysis and Interpretation

Table1 Frequency distribution of employees

S.NO	Socio-economic variables		Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	40	66
		Female	20	34
		Total	60	100
2	Salary	Below 10000	10	16
		10000-20000	17	28
		20000-30000	15	25
		30000-40000	10	16
		Above 40000	8	13
		Total	60	100
3	Marital status	Married	38	63
		Unmarried	22	37
		Total	60	100
4	Age	Below 20	15	25
		20-30	25	42
		30-40	10	16
		40-50	7	12
		Above 50	3	5
Total	60	100		
5	Experience	Below 5	7	12
		5-10	30	50
		10-15	15	25
		15-20	5	8
		Above 20	3	5
Total	60	100		
6	Qualification	SSLC	13	22
		Diploma	12	20
		UG	22	36
		PG	8	13
		Others	5	8
Total	60	100		

Source: primary data

The above table show than 66 % of the respondents are male and 34% of the respondents are female. 10% of the respondents are getting below 10000, 16 % of the respondents are getting 10000-20000, 28% of the respondents are getting 20000-30000, 25% of the respondents are getting 30000-40000 and 16% of the respondents are getting above 40000 salary. Nearly 63% of the respondents are married 37% respondents are unmarried.

From the table the study shows that 25% of the respondents are in the age group of below 20, 42% of the respondents are in the age group of 20-30, 16% of the respondents are in the age group of 30-40, 12% of the respondents are in the age group of 40-50 and 17% of the respondents are above 50 and most of the respondents are under graduates.

Table2 shows employee motivation and employees performance

Sample size	Factor 1	Factor 2	Calculated value	Interpretation
60	Employee motivation	Employee performance	r = -0.1242	Low degree of negative correlation

Source: primary data

From the above table r value is -0.1242 which shows a low degree of negative correlation. It was found that, there is no relationship between employee motivation and employee performance.

Conclusion

The study has been conducted at Solara Active Pharma Sciences Limited to find the level of employee motivation and to find the relationship between employee motivation and employee performance and employees motivation level at solara active pharma science limited is moderate. It was concluded that by using correlation, there is no relationship between employee motivation and employee performance. Employees feel that company have to provide sufficient medical facilities and transportation facilities to motivate the worker to perform their work effectively.

Reference

[1] Nabi, N., Islam, M., Dip, T. M., & Hassain, A. A. (2017). Impact of motivation on employee performances: a case study of Karmasangsthan bank Limited, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 57-78.

[2] Faisal Al Madi (2017) The Impact of Employee Motivation on Organizational Commitment *European Journal of Business and Management ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Vol.9, No.15, 2017)*

[3] Nguyen My, L. (2017). The Impact of Employees Motivation on Organizational Effectiveness.

[4] Dr. Ismail Nizam, Impact of Employee Motivation on Organizational Performance, *international Journal of Accounting & Business Management Vol. 3 (No.2), November, 2015 SSN: 2289-4519 DOI: 10.24924*

[5] Shoraj, D., & Llaci, S. (2015). Motivation and its impact on organizational effectiveness in Albanian businesses. *Sage Open*, 5(2), 2158244015582229.

[6] David Ackah (2014), The Impact of Motivation on Employee Performance *Global Journal of Management Studies and Researches*, 1 (5) 2014, ISSN 2345-6086

[7] Singh, A., & Singh, B. *International Journal OF Engineering Sciences & Management Research*.

